

CONSTITUTIONAL GUARANTEES OF REAL ESTATE ACTIVITY

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Abstract. The thesis talks about the positive experience of foreign countries in the field of real estate, which is directly related to the field of real estate today. Also, the thesis describes the norms of the state and description of real estate in other countries, in particular, the Russian Federation and a number of similar countries. The aim of the thesis was to regulate real estate-related legal regulation of real estate activities and to implement real estate-related issues. Also, the disclosure of problems arising in the field of real estate and its solution were discussed. In the conclusion, it was concluded that in the development of real estate activity, first of all, it is necessary to study foreign experience in the field of real estate regulation.

Keywords: Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan, development of market relations, is property, sub-legal documents, entrepreneurship and labor, legal protection.

The basis of the economy of Uzbekistan, aimed at the development of market relations, is property in various forms. Taking into account the primacy of consumer rights, the state guarantees freedom of economic activity, entrepreneurship and labor, equal rights of all forms of property and legal protection.

“Everyone has the right to own a home, no one can be deprived of their home without a court decision and contrary to the law, the value of the home to the owner who has been deprived of his home and the place of the damages he suffered is provided by law. In cases and in order, compensation in advance and in equal value is ensured¹” was confirmed in Article 47 of the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan adopted in the new version.

This rule, established as a constitutional norm, is reflected in the fact that the development of the market economy in our republic is based on different forms of ownership, especially in the guarantee of rights to immovable properties of a much higher value.

¹ <https://old.lex.uz/docs/-6445145>

The compliance of the legal documents and sub-legal documents of the Republic of Uzbekistan with the Constitution shows that the above-mentioned norm has a solid basis.

Relations related to land and real estate are closely related to real estate activity. In fact, it is necessary to first understand how these relations were formed. Accordingly, we will focus on the stages of establishing relations related to land and real estate in the regulation of real estate activity in the legislation.

If we turn to the history of our legislation, initially the relations related to land and real estate in our country were regulated by the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Land" adopted by the Supreme Council of the Republic of Uzbekistan² on June 20, 1990. The development of social relations, in particular, the processes of expropriation and privatization, which were carried out at a rapid pace in the country at that time, required the improvement of legislative documents in the regulation of this type of relations. For this reason, the current Land Code was adopted by the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Approval of the Land Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan". Also, with the adoption of the Resolution of the Oliy Majlis of the Republic of Uzbekistan on April 30, 1998 "On the Procedure for the Implementation of the Land Codex of the Republic of Uzbekistan", the previous Law "On Land" became invalid. The adoption of the Land Code led to a systematic regulation of land-related relations. In a general sense, the Land Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan is a set of norms providing the legal basis of real estate.

The Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Ownership" stipulates the inviolability of property, the right of every person to be an owner, the permission to have any form of ownership that creates an opportunity for the efficient operation of the economy and the growth of the people's well-being in the republic, the inviolability of all forms of ownership and the creation of equal conditions for their development, and The rights and guarantees that the Republic of Uzbekistan will create all the necessary conditions for the preservation and increase of the property belonging to the owner have been reflected. This law plays an important role in ensuring real estate and property rights to it. For the first time in the legislation of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Enterprises in the Republic of Uzbekistan" included the definition of the enterprise, which also applies to economic entities. According to it, a legal entity that produces and sells products

² In the article, the legal status and name of most of the state bodies and organizations have changed, and the names of most of the listed organizations have been updated today. Accordingly, the names of the organizations are given in the old form due to the stages of development of the legislation. The author.

or exchanges products, performs work, provides services based on the use of property owned by the right of ownership or the right to fully manage the economy, in accordance with the current laws, in the conditions of competition and equality of all forms of ownership an independent business entity that carries out its activities is an enterprise. However, this Law has become invalid based on the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated December 15, 2000 No. 175-II "On Amendments and Additions to Certain Legislative Documents of the Republic of Uzbekistan, as well as Declaring Some of the Laws as Repealed". Another aspect is that economic entities may not necessarily be commercial organizations, that is, non-governmental non-commercial organizations also have the right to own, use and dispose of their property.

Also, according to the current Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Cooperation"³, an independent economic entity that has the right of a legal entity, owns, uses and disposes of its own property based on the right of collective property is considered a cooperative.

In Article 2 of the Law "On Protection of the Rights of Joint-Stock Companies and Shareholders" (legal status of a joint-stock company): a joint-stock company is an economic entity whose charter fund is divided into a certain number of shares confirming the company's obligations to shareholders.

As can be seen from the above definitions, economic entities are commercial and non-commercial organizations with the status of a legal entity and their own property.

The process of privatization, which has been carried out in recent years in our country, is currently gaining great importance in the creation of private property of economic entities. Privatization is essentially the transfer of state-owned objects to individuals and legal entities. According to Y.A. Sukhanov, real estate belonging to the state on the basis of property rights is to be transferred to the private property of citizens and legal entities in accordance with the procedure established by special legal documents.⁴

Privatization is widely used in countries that were previously based on socialist production relations as one of the methods to ensure the transition from an economy based on administrative command to a free market economy. This process is a temporary transitional measure that serves the formation of private property, which is an important driving tool of the market economy, and the development of entrepreneurship.

³ Bulletin of the Supreme Council of the Republic of Uzbekistan, 1991, No. 8, Article 193.

⁴ Mattei U., Sukhanov E.A. Basic provisions of property rights. – M.: Lawyer, 1999.

From the first years of our country's independence, great attention was paid to the expropriation and privatization of property, which is considered a very important change in the path of economic reform, that is, reconstruction based on market laws. Taking into account the world experience, Uzbekistan's own privatization model was developed. The essence of this model is expressed in the following main principles: privatization is carried out step by step on the basis of its program; transfer of state property to another form of property, except for the cases provided for by law, only for a fee; social protection of all citizens in the conditions of privatization and granting of privileges to business entities, ensuring mutual equality of their rights. The legal basis for the implementation of the privatization process was the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Expropriation and Privatization⁵" adopted on October 19, 1991.

If we pay attention to the civil-legal aspect of privatization, privatization is one of the specific grounds for the cancellation of state property, in which state property is transferred to the property of state residents for a fee or free of charge. According to R.A. Mametova, privatization is the sale of state property to citizens, non-state and foreign legal entities according to the will of the state as the owner within the framework of special legal documents⁶.

With the adoption of the Civil Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan with the laws adopted on December 21, 1995 and August 29, 1998, a legal basis was created for real estate. Civil Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan

Article 83 (types of property), Article 84 (state registration of immovable property) and Article 85 (enterprise) gave legal status to real estate as a property complex. All real estate relations are now regulated based on these norms. Also, Article 212 of the Code (arbitrary construction of a building and its consequences) defined the definition and basis of an arbitrarily built building - immovable property.

In accordance with Article 4 of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Collateral" adopted on May 1, 1998, real estate can be collateral in the form of a mortgage. Also, the obligation to draw up a pledge agreement related to real estate in written form and the mortgage agreement to be notarized, as well as its procedure, was determined by Article 11 of the law (the form of the pledge agreement and its registration). Such a norm is also contained in the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Mortgages" adopted on October 4, 2006, which specifies the procedure for notarial approval and state registration of a mortgage contract (Article 12) and state registration of a mortgage (Article 13).

⁵ Bulletin of the Supreme Council of Uzbekistan, 1992, No. 1, Article 43.

⁶ Law and property. – Almaty: Zherti Zhargy, 1998. – P.43.

In the Law "On Collateral" enterprises are recognized as collateral along with real estate.

In order to ensure the effective functioning of the Republican Real Estate Exchange, the Cabinet of Ministers' Decision "On measures to ensure the effective functioning of the Republican Real Estate Exchange" established rules for the real estate sector. In particular, in this document, the State Property Committee of the former Republic of Uzbekistan together with ministries and agencies:

- formation of republican and regional real estate markets, including unfinished construction objects;
- sale of real estate objects based on state, branch and regional programs of expropriation and privatization;
- tasked with training real estate market specialists and improving their skills.

Based on the above facts, real estate activity in the real estate market we can see that it did not arise by itself.

We can witness that all adopted normative legal documents are directly related to real estate activity, and the inviolability of private property is constitutionally protected.

It is no exaggeration to say that real estate relations in the Republic of Uzbekistan have more potential for development, and for this purpose, the implementation of innovations in the legal system will be the result of today's research in the field of real estate.

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